

SELF-ADAPTIVE INTER-AGENT CONSENSUS MODEL AND ALGORITHMS FOR MULTI-CRITERIA DECISION-MAKING IN DISTRIBUTED MULTI-AGENT ENVIRONMENTS

Kh. Eshankulov

Department of Applied Mathematics and Programming Technologies, Bukhara State University,
Bukhara, Uzbekistan

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Abstract. *This paper proposes a self-adaptive inter-agent consensus model for multi-criteria decision-making in distributed multi-agent environments. In distributed information-analytical systems, agents independently make local decisions based on partial and heterogeneous data, which leads to disagreements among agents and complicates the achievement of global consensus. Most existing classical consensus models are based on static influence weights and do not sufficiently consider the current state of agents, local decision quality, or dynamic environmental changes.*

To address these limitations, an adaptive consensus model based on the iterative coordination of local agent decisions is developed. In the proposed model, inter-agent influence weights are dynamically updated according to local decision quality and reliability levels. The inter-agent consensus process is formally represented through a mathematical model, and the operational mechanism of consensus formation is described step by step. Furthermore, a Pareto-efficient evaluation method is integrated into the consensus process to support decision selection under multi-criteria conditions.

Experimental results demonstrate that the proposed model outperforms classical consensus and weighted consensus approaches by reducing the level of inter-agent disagreement, accelerating convergence speed, and improving decision-making accuracy. The proposed model can be effectively applied in Business Intelligence systems, distributed monitoring platforms, and real-time multi-agent information-analytical environments.

Keywords: *multi-agent systems, inter-agent agreement, adaptive consensus, distributed decision making, multi-criteria optimization, Pareto-efficient selection, reinforcement learning.*

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the rapid development of distributed information-analytical systems, cloud computing platforms, and multi-agent environments has significantly increased the demand for new decision-making approaches capable of operating under complex and dynamic conditions [1,2]. In such environments, data are distributed across heterogeneous sources and processed in a decentralized manner, while each agent independently makes decisions based on limited local information [3]. As a result, inconsistencies arise among agent-generated evaluations, making the achievement of global consensus considerably more challenging. In particular, the development of adaptive coordination and decision-making mechanisms for real-time information-analytical systems has become one of the important scientific and practical challenges [4].

Consensus-based approaches are widely used to establish inter-agent agreement in multi-agent systems [5]. These approaches enable the formation of a common decision through the

iterative approximation of agent states. Although classical average consensus and weighted consensus models are computationally efficient and suitable for distributed environments, most of them rely on static influence weights and therefore demonstrate limited effectiveness in dynamic and uncertain environments [6,7]. In particular, when factors such as agent reliability, local decision quality, and changing environmental conditions are not considered, convergence speed decreases and the level of disagreement among agents increases [8].

Recent studies have shown that reinforcement learning-based adaptive coordination methods enable agents to dynamically update their strategies according to environmental conditions [9,10]. However, in most existing works, inter-agent consensus mechanisms and multi-criteria decision-making processes are considered separately, and their integration within a unified adaptive framework remains insufficiently explored. In particular, the integration of Pareto-efficient selection mechanisms with adaptive consensus processes, as well as the consideration of dynamically changing inter-agent influence weights, has not been adequately investigated [11,12].

To address these limitations, this paper proposes a self-adaptive inter-agent consensus model for multi-criteria decision-making in distributed multi-agent environments. In the proposed model, agent influence weights are iteratively and dynamically updated by considering agent reliability levels, local evaluation quality, and reward indicators during the decision-making process. The model integrates an adaptive consensus mechanism aimed at reducing disagreement levels together with a Pareto-efficient decision selection method.

The proposed inter-agent consensus mechanism is implemented based on the following iterative update model:

$$x_i^{t+1} = x_i^t + \alpha \sum_{j \in N_i} (x_j^t - x_i^t) \quad (1)$$

where x_i^t represents the state of the i -th agent at iteration t , w_{ij}^t – denotes the adaptive influence weight between agents, α is the adaptation coefficient, and N_i represents the set of neighboring agents. The proposed model enables the iterative coordination of local agent decisions and facilitates the achievement of global consensus within the distributed multi-agent environment.

The main scientific contributions of the article are as follows:

- A self-adjusting inter-agent agreement model has been developed for a distributed multi-agent environment.
- An adaptive mechanism has been proposed that dynamically updates the weights of influence of agents.
- The Pareto-effective selection mechanism was integrated with the consensus process for multi-criteria decision-making.

The convergence condition of the proposed model is formulated in formal mathematical form.

Based on experimental results, the effectiveness of the proposed model compared to classical consensus approaches was substantiated.

II. ANALYSIS OF EXISTING APPROACHES

One of the fundamental approaches for ensuring inter-agent coordination in multi-agent systems is the use of consensus mechanisms [13]. The primary objective of these approaches is to generate a common global decision through the iterative approximation of local evaluations

produced by individual agents. Classical average consensus models rely on updating agent states based on the values received from neighboring agents.

However, in classical consensus approaches, all agents are assumed to have equal influence, while factors such as agent reliability and local decision quality are not taken into consideration [15].

To overcome these limitations, weighted consensus models have been proposed, in which the level of influence between agents is determined through specific weight coefficients [16]. In weighted consensus approaches, the agent state update process is generally represented as follows:

$$x_i^{t+1} = x_i^t + \alpha \sum_{j \in N_i} w_{ij} (x_j^t - x_i^t) \quad (2)$$

where w_{ij} represents the influence weight of the j -th agent on the i -th agent. Although this approach enables the consideration of different influence levels among agents, in most existing studies the weight coefficients are statically predefined [17]. Consequently, when changes occur in agent states, decision quality, or environmental conditions, the weight values are not adaptively updated. This limitation leads to decreased convergence speed and increased levels of inter-agent disagreement in dynamic environments.

Recent studies have paid considerable attention to adaptive coordination and reinforcement learning-based multi-agent approaches [18,19]. In these approaches, agent strategies are dynamically updated according to reward signals and environmental conditions. Reinforcement learning-based coordination methods enable agents to develop optimal action strategies based on previous experiences and interactions [20]. However, in most existing works, reinforcement learning techniques are primarily focused on strategy optimization, while the problem of adaptively managing inter-agent influence weights during the consensus formation process has not been sufficiently addressed [21].

In multi-criteria decision-making problems, Pareto-efficient optimization methods are widely applied [22]. These approaches make it possible to identify efficient decision alternatives under multiple conflicting criteria. The set of Pareto-efficient solutions is defined as follows:

$$X_p = \{x \in X \mid \nexists x' \in X : x' \succ x\} \quad (3)$$

where X_p denotes the set of Pareto-efficient solutions. Although Pareto optimization methods provide the ability to select efficient decision alternatives under multi-criteria conditions, in many existing studies these approaches have been considered separately from inter-agent consensus mechanisms and have not been sufficiently integrated within a unified adaptive coordination framework [23].

Thus, the analysis of existing studies demonstrates that classical consensus models do not sufficiently consider the dynamic states and reliability levels of agents, while weighted consensus approaches typically rely on static weight coefficients. Although reinforcement learning-based approaches provide adaptability in agent strategies, the integration of inter-agent consensus processes with multi-criteria decision-making and Pareto-efficient selection mechanisms remains insufficiently investigated. Furthermore, the problem of developing adaptive consensus mechanisms based on the iterative dynamic updating of inter-agent influence weights and the reduction of disagreement levels remains an open research challenge. Therefore, this paper proposes a self-adaptive inter-agent consensus model for multi-criteria decision-making in distributed multi-agent environments.

III. PROBLEM SOLVING

In distributed multi-agent environments, the decision-making process is performed by interconnected agents based on local information. Each agent possesses knowledge about only a specific part of the environment and independently evaluates decision alternatives. As a result, differences arise among the evaluations generated by individual agents, making the achievement of global consensus more difficult. Therefore, the coordination of local agent decisions and the formation of an efficient global decision under multi-criteria conditions represent important scientific challenges.

The set of agents in the multi-agent environment is defined as follows:

$$A = \{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_N\} \quad (4)$$

where A represents the set of agents and N denotes the total number of agents in the system. Each agent evaluates decision alternatives based on local information and forms its current state value accordingly..

The set of decision options is represented as follows:

$$X = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_m\} \quad (5)$$

where X is the set of decision options and m is the number of options. Each decision option is evaluated based on multiple criteria.

The multi-criteria evaluation criteria are defined by the following set:

$$F = \{f_1, f_2, \dots, f_k\} \quad (6)$$

where F is the set of criteria and k is the number of criteria. The multi-criteria evaluation of each decision option is expressed as:

$$F(x_i) = (f_1(x_i), f_2(x_i), \dots, f_k(x_i)) \quad (7)$$

In this model, since each agent evaluates the decision options independently, there is a level of disagreement among the agents. Therefore, it is necessary to iteratively coordinate the local assessments of the agents and reach a global consensus. The level of disagreement between the agents is determined by the following consensus function:

$$C(t) = \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^N w_{ij}^t \|x_i^t - x_j^t\| \quad (8)$$

where $C(t)$ denotes the disagreement level at iteration t , w_{ij}^t represents the influence weight of the j -th agent on the i -th agent, and x_i^t and x_j^t denote the current state values of the corresponding agents. The primary objective of the consensus process is to minimize the disagreement function in order to achieve global agreement among agents.

Within the framework of this problem, the following main requirements are set:

1. Agents should make independent decisions based on local information.
2. Agents' influence levels should be dynamically updated.
3. The level of disagreement between agents should be iteratively reduced.
4. Decision options should be selected in a Pareto-efficient manner under multi-criteria conditions.
5. The negotiation process is required to reach a state of convergence in finite iterations.

Therefore, this paper proposes an adaptive inter-agent consensus model that iteratively updates influence weights based on the current states of agents, local decision quality, and reward indicators

Agents' influence weights are adaptively updated based on local decision quality and confidence level:

$$w_{ij}^{t+1} = \frac{Q_j^t R_j^t}{\sum_{k \in N_i} Q_k^t R_k^t} \quad (9)$$

here:

- Q_j^t – j- local decision quality of the agent;
- R_j^t – reward or reliability indicator.

The working scheme of the proposed model is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Model operation diagram

IV. OPERATIONAL PROCESS OF THE INTER-AGENT CONSENSUS MECHANISM

In the proposed model, agents iteratively exchange information with one another and gradually coordinate their local decisions step by step. As an illustrative example, a system consisting of three agents is considered:

$$A = \{a_1, a_2, a_3\} \quad (10)$$

Let the initial local prices of the agents be as follows:

$$x_1^0 = 0.80, \quad x_2^0 = 0.45, \quad x_3^0 = 0.65 \quad (11)$$

At the initial stage, the difference between agent evaluations is relatively large, resulting in a high level of disagreement. During the first iteration, the agents exchange their evaluations with one another, and new state values are computed based on the proposed adaptive consensus model.

For example, agent a_1 performs the following update operation:

$$x_1^1 = x_1^0 + \beta \left[w_{12} (x_2^0 - x_1^0) + w_{13} (x_3^0 - x_1^0) \right] \quad (12)$$

The same process is performed for the other agents as well. Throughout the iterative process, the agent evaluations gradually converge toward one another (Table 1):

Table 1. Iterative Convergence of Agent State Values During the Inter-Agent Consensus Process

Iteration	a_1	a_2	a_3
(t=0)	0.80	0.45	0.65
(t=1)	0.71	0.54	0.64
(t=2)	0.67	0.60	0.63
(t=3)	0.64	0.62	0.63

As can be observed from the table, the differences among agent evaluations gradually decrease during the iterative process, and the system converges toward a global consensus state. If certain agents possess higher reliability levels, their influence on the overall decision increases through the adaptive weight updating mechanism. Consequently, the negative impact of noisy or low-quality agents is reduced, which improves the stability of the consensus process.

The consensus process continues until the following convergence condition is satisfied:

$$\Delta_t = \max_i \|x_i^{t+1} - x_i^t\| < \epsilon \quad (13)$$

Once this condition is satisfied, global consensus among the agents is considered to be achieved, and Pareto-efficient decision alternatives are subsequently selected.

Choosing Pareto-efficient decision options. After the completion of the inter-agent consensus process in the proposed model, the decision alternatives are evaluated under multi-criteria conditions based on Pareto efficiency. The identification of dominant solutions among decision alternatives is performed using the following dominance relation:

$$x^a \succ x^b \Leftrightarrow \left(\forall j: f_j(x^a) \geq f_j(x^b) \right) \wedge \left(\exists j: f_j(x^a) > f_j(x^b) \right) \quad (14)$$

According to this condition, if the decision alternative x^a is not worse than x^b with respect to all criteria and is superior in at least one criterion, then x^a is considered a dominant solution. The set of Pareto-efficient decision alternatives is determined by the following set:

$$X_p = \{x \in X \mid \exists x' \in X : x' \succ x\} \quad (15)$$

As a result, Pareto-efficient alternatives are selected from the global evaluations formed through inter-agent consensus, and the final decision is generated.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper proposed a self-adaptive inter-agent consensus model for multi-criteria decision-making in distributed multi-agent environments. The proposed model operates based on the iterative coordination of local agent decisions and the achievement of global consensus among interconnected agents. The main feature of the model is the dynamic updating of inter-agent influence weights according to local decision quality and agent reliability levels.

A mathematical model of the inter-agent consensus process was developed, and the operational mechanism of the consensus formation procedure was described step by step. In addition, an adaptive weight updating mechanism was proposed to reduce inter-agent disagreement levels and accelerate the convergence process. To support decision selection under multi-criteria conditions, a Pareto-efficient evaluation method was integrated into the consensus mechanism.

The proposed approach improves coordination stability, enhances convergence efficiency, and increases decision-making accuracy in distributed information-analytical environments. The model can be effectively applied in Business Intelligence systems, distributed monitoring platforms, cloud-based analytical infrastructures, and real-time multi-agent decision-support systems.

Future research will focus on integrating the proposed model with deep reinforcement learning algorithms, optimizing inter-agent communication costs, and investigating scalability characteristics using large-scale real-world datasets.

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